

REINFORCING

Responsible tEerritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

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The REINFORCING project

- REINFORCING aims to become the Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) **central point of knowledge and expertise** that supports territories and institutions in fostering Fair Transitions governance by aligning with societal values, needs and expectations.
- **REINFORCING One-Stop Source** platform acts as catalyzer of the quadruple-helix community, who will co-develop services, including policy recommendations.
- The project supports **institutional changes** aiming at responsible sustainability transitions through **96 grants** dedicated to boost institutions scaling up their ORRI capacities, and to support European regions experimenting with ORRI.
- In addition, **mentoring and matchmaking services** and training modules will be provided and a **Global ORRI Network** will be established.

REINFORCING

REINFORCING APPROACH

**CONSOLIDATE
EVIDENCE BASE**

And

**DEVELOP
INNOVATIVE
GUIDANCE**

WP1 and WP2

**FINANCIAL
SUPPORT TO
THIRD PARTIES**

WP4

**CENTRAL POINT
OF EXPERTISE
AND
SUPPORT
SERVICES**

WP3

**EVALUATE IMPACTS AND
POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS**

WP5

WP6

**RAISE AWARENESS AND CO-
OPERATION WITH OTHER PROJECTS**

REINFORCING

REINFORCING WORK PLAN STRUCTURE

REINFORCING

TARGETS

New ORRI enablers

HEU projects

**REINFORCING
grantees**

MEASURES

One-stop source

WP3

Grants

WP4

Support services

**WP3,
WP4**

Training

WP3

REINFORCING

GRANTS

ORRI BOOSTER (12x4)

OPEN INNOVATION +3

ORRI INCUBATORS (8x3)

BALKANS, MISSIONS +1

REINFORCING

SUPPORT SERVICES

MATCHMAKING – MAP (WP4)

**ORRI Facilitators
ORRI ambassadors**

PATHWAYS (WP3)

15 SETS

MENTORING (WP3)

For ORRI Incubators

REINFORCING

TRAINING

TRAIN THE GRANTEES

CRASH COURSES

CLINICS

REINFORCING

REINFORCING METHODOLOGY

REINFORCING

REINFORCING CONSORTIUM

REINFORCING

THANK YOU

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